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January 14th, 2020

Editorial

Dear supporter,

We begin our third newsletter with the SUN-ERGY photo contest that SUNRISE is holding in collaboration with ENERGY-X. Please remind that the **deadline for entries is tomorrow, January 15**.

Next comes our key upcoming event: the SUN-ERGY kick-off event, which will be held in Brussels on February 5-6. We also include the latest opportunities in the areas of solar energy, artificial photosynthesis, and more. Finally, we cover the main highlights of the project during these past 3 months.

The SUNRISE Team

SUN-ERGY Photo Contest

THEME: RENEWABLE ENERGIES' CONVERSION AND STORAGE INTO CLEAN FUELS AND CHEMICALS

Open to PhD students and postdoctoral researchers!

Upcoming Events

SUN-ERGY Kick-off Event

On February 5-6, 2019 there will be the official kick-off of SUN-ERGY, a large-scale, integrated R&I initiative in the area of fossil-free fuels and chemicals. SUN-ERGY stems from two European flagship...

Opportunities in the Field

Disruptive photonics technologies

Deadline: April 22, 2020

The challenge is the development of advanced photonics technologies which have the potential to revolutionise an existing application sector or to create completely new applications and markets...

International cooperation with Japan for Research and Innovation on advanced biofuels and alternative renewable fuels

Deadline: September 1, 2020

Disruptive conversion technologies are needed for replacing completely ...

EIC prize: Fuel from the Sun, artificial photosynthesis

Deadline: first quarter, 2021

The challenge is to build a fully functional, bench-scale prototype of an artificial photosynthesis based system which can...

[See more opportunities](#)

Third Trimester Highlights: News

SUNRISE releases its technological roadmap to a clean-energy EU

With the release of this key outcome, SUNRISE aims at promoting a large-scale research initiative to provide short and long-term solutions to enable the transition to a circular economy powered by sunlight...

The potential of a sustainable production of fuels and key chemicals

This was the name of the lunchtime conference organized by the Directorate General for Energy (DG Energy) on October 24, 2019. The goal was to present...

SUNRISE's booth rocks at COP25!

Over 800 visitors dropped by SUNRISE's booth at the Green Zone of COP25 (United Nations Climate Change Conference) in Madrid, between 5-7 December, 2019. Our volunteers had the chance to...

Discussing solar fuels and chemicals at the Solar-to-products symposium

Storing and converting solar energy in sustainable fuels and chemical

products is SUNRISE's main aim to facilitate the transition from a linear to a circular economy. This is why SUNRISE coordinator Huub...

From fossil to renewable fuels: Interview with Hlne Lepaumier

When asked about the future of the sustainable energy, Hlne Lepaumier is optimistic: "Moving away from the use of fossil fuels will be a long process, but it is definitely feasible if we have cheap..."

Breaking down the artificial photosynthesis: Interview with Huub de Groot

During the SUNRISE consortium meeting held in May in Bologna (Italy), we had the chance to interview our coordinator Huub de Groot. As a professor at Leiden University, Huub is an expert in biophysical...

[See more news](#)

Third Trimester Highlights: Meetings

SUNRISE France stakeholder workshop

Over 75 stakeholders took part in the French SUNRISE Stakeholder Workshop under the aegis of ANCRE, the National Alliance for Energy Research on October 8, 2019, in Paris...

SUNRISE consortium & Mission Innovation meeting

On October 9-11, members of the SUNRISE consortium and Mission Innovation met at the offices of the initiative's partner EERA in Brussels. During the meeting, we had the chance to [interview Dr. Jafarian...](#)

ENERGY-X stakeholder workshop

ENERGY-X organized a strategic Stakeholder Workshop in Frankfurt on December 2, 2019 in collaboration with SUNRISE. Both initiatives will merge to continue as SUN-ERGY as of March 2020, in order to...

SUNRISE Finland stakeholder workshop

Following other previous national workshops, such as the [Italian](#), [Polish](#), or [Swiss](#) ones, 65 attendees from all the SUNRISE official supporter organisations in Finland...

[See more meetings](#)

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